

AN INTEGRATED REVIEW ON A GLOBAL EMERGENCY: LUMPY SKIN DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Currently lumpy skin disease (LSD) has emerged as a significant transboundary viral disease affecting cattle and buffaloes, with profound economic and animal health implications worldwide. It has rapidly expanded into Asia, Europe and middle East countries. Control measures have predominantly focused on vaccination campaigns with varying degree of success. However, challenges persist, including vaccine accessibility, cold chain maintenance and farmer compliance. Economically repercussions are substantial, encompassing direct losses from livestock morbidity and mortality. As this disease is primarily transmitted through blood- feeding vectors such as mosquitoes and stable flies leading to cutaneous nodules, fever and decreased milk production in affected animals. This present review emphasizes the necessity for a coordinated global response, integrating surveillance rapid diagnostics, effective vaccination strategies

and public awareness campaigns to educate the livestock holders about the prevalence of LSD.

KEYWORDS: Lumpy skin disease, Transboundary, Mortality and Morbidity.

INTRODUCTION

As the current world is facing drastic pandemic conditions due to wide spread of viruses not only in humans even in cattle. So, it is essential to check the prevalence of diseases with its risk rate and recently world is facing a panic situation in cattle because of lumpy skin disease. Lumpy skin disease is caused by lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV) of Capri poxvirus genus, sub family Chordoprvirirniae, family Poxviridae. The disease is known by various names such as “LSD”, “Pseudo- urticaria”, Neethling Virus Disease”, “Exanthema nodularis bovis” and Knopvelsiekte. LSD is a non-zoonotic, vector borne and transboundary disease with limited host range and currently restricted to ruminants viz. cattle and water buffalos.^[1]

LSD symptoms in cattle are mild to severe; characterized by fever, multiple skin nodules covering the neck, back, perineum, tail, limbs and genital organs, the mucous membranes; the lesion may also involve subcutaneous tissues and sometimes musculature and internal organs. Affected animals also exhibit lameness, emaciation and cessation of milk production.^[2] Cattle breeds of both sexes and all ages are susceptible to LSDV, but there is some evidence to support that young animal may be more susceptible to the severe form of the disease. It has been recently reported from China and Bangladesh sharing borders with India. The disease is endemic in African countries but recently the disease has been reported from new territories around the world.^[3]

The virus is stable in ambient conditions for long period. It can persist in desiccated skin crusts for 35 days, in necrotic nodules for 33 days and in air- dried hides for at least 18 days. Iatrogenic route can be another route of spread of virus when single needle used for mass vaccination that can acquire the virus from the skin scabs or crusts.^[4]

The first description of the clinical signs of LSD was in 1929 in Zambia. In the beginning, LSD signs were considered to be the consequence either of poisoning or a hypersensitivity to insect bites. Death rates are higher among calves. It is reported in Madagascar and some countries in the Arab Gulf Peninsula and Middle East. Recently, the disease is reported in LSD free countries with potential economic loss to the livestock industry. LSD causes loss of milk and beef production, absorptions in females and sterility in males.^[5]

STABILITY OF VIRUS^[6]

The virus is stable in environmental conditions like temperature, air pressure, humidity, noise amplitude, light intensity and vibration magnitude. The virus is destroyed in sunlight and lipid detergents. Arrange the sheds and stores for effected animals it may give the protection from virus. And also separate the animals by their health condition. Based on the skin condition of the animal, the virus gets destroyed in different number of days like 33 days, 35 days, 18 days etc.

TRANSMISSION^[7]

The disease has been observed to appeared following the seasonal rains, when there is always an increase in the population of different arthropod species. The onset of frosts in south Africa and Egypt results in a great fall in the number of cases of LSD, which virtually disappears over the winter to reappear again in the spring and summer. The most important source of infection to healthy animals is considered to be skin lesions or nodules since the

virus persists in the lesions or scabs for long periods of time and has strong tropism to dermal issues.

One of the main reasons for the transmission of the virus is to allow the same syringe needle for two or more animals. And the other reason is the virus is transmitted by biting flies and mosquitoes. And also, the virus is transmitted by effected animals also. The transmission of virus is divided into two route ways. The first one is short route of transmission and another route is long route of transmission.

SHORT ROUTE OF TRANSMISSION^[8]

In the short route of transmission, infected vectors like ticks, flies, mosquitoes etc., whenever there are climate changes, they bite healthy animals and then transmit the virus into their body. This is the short route of transmission of virus. The virus spreads quickly from infected virus.

LONG ROUTE OF TRANSMISSION

In the long route of transmission, the infected animals are moving one place to another place, they carry virus into healthy animals. The virus is spread in animals by their saliva, mouth and nose secretions, sharing the food and water and sometimes use same needles for other animals also spreads virus.

SHORT AND LONG ROUTE OF TRANSMISSION

Symptoms of lumpy skin disease

High fever (up to 41⁰C)

Eye/Nasal discharge (Excess Saliva)

Abortion in pregnancy cows

Loss of appetite

Drop in milk production.

TREATMENT^[9]

Lumpy skin disease is caused by virus. The disease is seen in cows, buffalos, cattle etc., In cattle small number of nodules are present at different spots. Cows and buffalos have innumerable nodules up to 3cm in diameter. Firstly, the disease can be confirmed with a laboratory test to detect virus or antibodies.

There is no treatment for LSD. But vaccination is the one of the virus controls for lumpy skin disease. Non-steroidal Anti Inflammatories and antibiotics are treated for lumpy skin disease. The treatment is divided into two types.

1. Allopathic treatment.
2. Herbal treatment.
3. Homeopathy treatment.

Allopathic treatment

Antiseptic with herbal spray. It is used for the infected animals to clean and prevent wounds.

Levamisole (immunomodulatory drug). It is helpful to protect against viral infection and also improves the immune system.

Antihistamines (10 ml daily for three days). It may give the relief from allergic reactions, wound swelling and itching. It may give the relief from

Antibiotics ex: Amoxicillin at the dose of 3-4 gm total or 10-12 mg per kg body weight. Antibodies are used to control and prevent the viral infection.

Herbal treatment**First method**

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY
1	Betel leaves	10
2	Black pepper	10g
3	Salt	10g
4	Jaggery	Quantity Sufficient

Divide the paste into small portions and feed infected animals orally. Administer the herbal paste into three doses daily every three hours and change the doses after first day. The treatment continued for 2 weeks.

Second method

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY
1	Garlic	2 pearls
2	Coriander	10g
3	Cumin	10g
4	Tulsi	1 handful
5	Dry cinnamon leaves	10g
6	Black pepper	10g
7	Betel leaves	5
8	Bulbs of Shallots	2
9	Turmeric powder	10g
10	Chirata leaf powder	30g
11	Sweet Basil	1 handful
12	Neem leaves	1 handful
13	Aegle marmalos	1 handful
14	Jaggery	100g

Divide the paste into small portions and provide animals orally. Administer the herbal paste into single dose every three hours in evening times and two doses in the morning after first day.

Third method

This method is used for external application.

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY
1	Acalypha indica leaves	1 handful
2	Pearls of Garlic	10
3	Neem leaves	1 handful
4	Coconut (or) sesame oil	500ml
5	Turmeric	20g
6	Mehendi and Tulasi leaves	1 handful

Mix the total content and boil, after cooling apply direct to wound after cleaning.

Homeopathy Treatment^[10]

Effectiveness of Homeopathy in lumpy skin disease- A review of experimental evidence [January 2023] Yogeshwari Gupta, Samridhi Sharma et al.

In Homeopathy treatment, to control the disease, preventive measures need to be implemented, which includes Restricted movement of infected animals with LSD and Restrict vector movements which may cause disease transmission.

In homeopathy, different health conditions have its own specific treatment. **Merc sol** is used for eruption and ulcers, **Silicea** is used for pustular discharge and painful abscess, **Pulsatilla** is used for reduced appetite, thirst and fever along with eruption and finally **Kali iod** is used for bloody eruption, boils and abscess.

The other homeopathy medicines are Rhus Toxicodendron-30 C, Thunja Occidentalis-30C, Arsenicum album-30C, Pulsatilla-30 C combined and given 10 drops three times a day. After the animal received medication for two days. After that seeing the improvement in appetite and disappearing of skin nodules.

Prevention And Control^[11,12]

Quarantine and Movement control

This is the first implemented action for controlling LSD. Infected animals should be kept in one room and healthy animals in another room. Because LSD spreads by biting flies and certain ticks. The rooms should be kept clean and food should be given separately.

Mosquito Repellents

Mosquito repellents can be an aid in the prevention of the spread of the LSD. Regular insecticides and insect repellents for cows and buffaloes along with other pest control methods can help control vectors farm buildings and grounds.

Vaccination

Vaccination is the best method for preventing the spread of LSD. Live vaccines help control losses from lumpy skin disease in endemic areas.

Awareness Programmes

To conduct programmes about LSD, why does this disease occur and how does it spread. And also, to inform about the signs and symptoms, disease prevention, quarantine methods, vaccinations etc., It may give the knowledge of the LSD.

CONCLUSION

Lumpy skin disease has rapidly transformed from a regionally confined ailment of cattle into a major transboundary animal disease with profound economic trade and food security implications according global health India alerts the evidence of its swift expansion is witnessed across Africa, Asia and middle east and currently spreading towards Europe which highlights the urgency for integrated, science driven control strategies.

High coverage vaccination, rapid diagnostics, vector management and coordinated movement restrictions remain the cornerstones of out break control, but these must be coupled with international collaboration, standardized surveillance and equitable access to vaccines and diagnostic tools. As this disease is taking lives of calf more reportedly. There is a need to address gaps in vector ecology. Vaccine efficacy and modelling tools is essential for long term preparedness to face these global medical emergencies. So, it requires collective vigilance and harmonized action to safeguard the health of live stock in rural and urban livelihoods to maintain global trade stability ultimately.

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